

the basis of microanalysis, spectral data (uv, ir, pmr) and comparison with authentic samples in known cases.

Experimental

All melting points were observed on a Koflar apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were obtained in KBr with a Pye-Unicam SP3-100 spectrophotometer. Uv spectra were recorded on a Pye-Unicam PU-8800 spectrophotometer. Pmr spectra were run in CCl_4 on a Varian A60 instrument with Me_4Si as the internal standard.

Beckmann rearrangement of the oxime 1: A suspension of the oxime 1 (2.0 g) in acetic anhydride (15 ml) was treated with BF_3 -etherate (5 ml) during a period of 15 min with mechanical stirring. The dark solution thus obtained was kept for 1 h at 10-15° and then at room temperature overnight. The mixture was poured into 50 ml of chilled water. The resulting oily material was extracted with ether and washed with water, sodium bicarbonate solution (5%) and again with water. The organic layer was dried over sodium sulphate (anhydrous) and evaporated to dryness. The oily residue was chromatographed over silica gel (40 g). Elution with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (7 : 1) afforded 4 which was recrystallised from methanol (0.9 g, 45%), m.p. 171° (lit.⁹ 171°) (Found : C, 74.70 ; H, 10.11 ; N, 3.20. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{44}\text{NOCl}$ calcd. for : C, 74.74 ; H, 10.15 ; N, 3.23%).

Further elution with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (3 : 1) gave 5, which was recrystallised from methanol (0.75 g, 37.5%), m.p. 170° (lit.⁵ 170-71°) (Found : C, 81.61 ; H, 10.79 ; N, 3.50. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{43}\text{NO}$ calcd. for : C, 81.61 ; H, 10.83 ; N, 3.52%).

Beckmann rearrangement of the oxime 2: The oxime 2 (2.0 g) on treatment with BF_3 -etherate (5 ml) in acetic anhydride (15 ml) afforded two products on tlc. After usual work up of the reaction mixture, the oily residue was chromatographed over silica gel (40 g). Elution with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (10 : 1) provided 6 which was recrystallised from methanol (0.65 g, 32.5%), m.p. 103° (Found : C, 74.51 ; H, 9.80 ; N, 2.80. $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{49}\text{NO}_2$ calcd. for : C, 74.55 ; H, 9.82 ; N, 2.80%) ; λ_{max} (CH_3OH) 223 nm ; ν_{max} (KBr) 1740 (CH_3COO), 1690 (CO-N), 1670, 1620 (C=C-CO-N), 1240 and 1040 cm^{-1} (C-O) ; δ (CCl_4) 6.0 (1H, s, C_6 -H), 4.55 (1H, mc, C_8 - α -H), 3.25 (1H, m, C_8 -H), 1.98 (3H, s, CH_3COO), 1.85 (3H, s, CH_3CO), 1.12 (3H, s, C_{10} - CH_3), 0.80 (3H, s, C_{13} - CH_3), 0.93 and 0.96 (remaining methyl protons).

Continued elution with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (4 : 1) furnished 7 which was recrystallised from petroleum ether (0.9 g, 45%), m.p. 196° (lit.⁶ 197-98°) (Found : C, 75.97 ; H, 10.26 ; N, 3.05. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{47}\text{NO}_2$ calcd. for : C, 76.15 ; H, 10.28, N, 3.06%).

Beckmann rearrangement of the oxime 3: The reaction of the oxime 3 (2.0 g) with BF_3 -etherate (5 ml) in acetic anhydride (15 ml) was carried out as described above. The residue was chromatographed over silica gel (40 g). Elution with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (8 : 1) afforded 8 which was recrystallised from methanol (0.8 g, 40.0%), m.p. 123° (Found : C, 79.26 ; H, 10.24 ; N, 3.18. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{45}\text{NO}_2$ calcd. for : C, 79.27 ; H, 10.25 ; N, 3.19%) ; λ_{max} (CH_3OH) 272 nm ; ν_{max} (KBr) 1695 (CO-N), 1670 and 1610 cm^{-1} (C=C-CO-N) ; δ (CCl_4) 6.0 (2H, br s, C_8 -H and C_4 -H), 5.58 (1H, s, C_6 -H), 3.3 (1H, m, C_8 -H), 2.07 (3H, s, CH_3CO), 1.12 (3H, s, C_{10} - CH_3), 0.74 (3H, s, C_{13} - CH_3), 0.83, and 0.91 (other methyl protons).

Continued elution with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (3 : 1) gave the product 5 which was recrystallised from methanol (0.7 g, 35.0%), m.p. 170° (lit.⁵ 170-71°).

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Synthesis of some Di-, Tri- and Tetra-peptides containing Methionine, Valine and Glycine

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METHIONINE is frequently present in biologically active polypeptides, e.g. ACTH, MSH, bradykinin and elediosin^{1,2}. Recently, we have reported the synthesis of *N*-tosylamino acids and dipeptide derivatives and some compounds were found to display antimicrobial activities³⁻⁵. In view of the above observations and in continuation of our studies in the same field³⁻⁵, we synthesised a new series of *N*-tosyl-di-, -tri- and -tetra-peptides (3-33) containing methionine, valine, and glycine

with different sequences. The synthetic peptides (3-33) are necessary intermediate compounds for subsequent synthesis of higher peptides analogous to some antibiotics and other pharmacologically active compounds. The biological activity of the synthesised peptides (3-33) and their copper(II) complexes has been studied.

L-Methionine methyl ester hydrochloride (1) was prepared using the thionyl chloride method and obtained in higher yield (90%) than that reported earlier^{6,7}. The synthesis of methionyl- and methionine-peptides was achieved by the application of HCl, L-Met-OMe (1) and Tos-L-Met (2) via the DCC method and no side reaction was observed. *N*-Tosyldipeptide methyl esters (3-9) were prepared in good yields (55-73%) using DCC. Treatment of these dipeptide methyl esters with methanol saturated with ammonia afforded the desired *N*-tosyldipeptide amides (10-13). However, it was observed that during the synthesis of Tos-L-Met-L-Met-NH₂ (10) a byproduct was isolated, which was recrystallised from methanol, (15%), mp. 221-23° (Found : N, 14.39. C₁₁H₂₁N₃O₂S₂ requires : N, 14.40%); R_f 0.31, [α]_D²⁰ + 10.2 (C, 0.1 LMF); gave positive ninhydrin reaction and was identified as L-Met-L-Met-NH₂. The remaining *N*-tosyldipeptide amides (11-13) were chromatographically homogeneous and did not respond to ninhydrin reaction.

Hydrazinolysis of the methyl esters (3-9) in methanol or ethanol gave the corresponding *N*-tosyldipeptide hydrazides (14-20).

The reaction of Tos-Gly-Gly (22) with L-Met-OMe.HCl (1) and Tos-L-Met (2) with HCl. Gly-Gly-OMe (21) in the presence of DCC gave the corresponding tripeptides (23 and 24). Synthesis of *N*-tosyltripeptide methyl esters (25-29) was achieved starting from the hydrazides (14-20), which were converted into the corresponding dipeptide azides. The azides on coupling with amino acid methyl esters gave the tripeptide derivatives (25-29), which were easily isolated and purified. The protected tetrapeptides (32, 33) were prepared in 70-72% yield by the treatment of Tos-Gly-Gly-Gly (31) with HCl. L-Met-OMe (1), and Tos-L-Met (2) with HCl. Gly-Gly-Gly-OMe (1), and Tos-L-Met (2) with HCl. Gly-Gly-Gly-OMe (30) using DCC.

The dipeptide methyl esters (3-9) containing L-methionine as the N- or C-terminal amino acid in the dipeptide gave deep blue coloured 1:1 complexes with Cu^{II} (λ_{max} 620-640 nm). The dipeptide amides (10-13) gave deep violet coloured 1:1 complexes with Cu^{II} (λ_{max} 560-575 nm). Similarly, the dipeptide hydrazides (14-20) gave violet coloured 1:1 complexes with Cu^{II} (λ_{max} 560-575 nm). A comparison of the blue copper complexes of *N*-tosyldipeptide methyl esters with violet copper complexes of their corresponding dipeptide amides and dipeptide hydrazides strongly supports the view that the amide and hydrazide groups participate in the complex formation of dipeptide amides and dipeptide hydrazides of

methionine. Similar observations have been reported by us⁸⁻¹¹ in the case of copper(II) complexes of di- and tri-peptide amides and hydrazides of serine, glycine, lysine and ornithine. The tripeptide methyl esters (23-29) gave pale violet or deep violet coloured 1:1 complexes with Cu^{II} (λ_{max} 560-570 nm). The tetrapeptide methyl esters (32, 33) gave red or reddish violet coloured 1:1 complexes with Cu^{II} (λ_{max} 540-550 nm).

From the above results, it is evident that the di-, tri-, and tetra-peptide methyl esters containing methionine form normal complexes with Cu^{II} as has been observed for di-, tri- and tetra-peptides of glycine and alanine¹². However, in the case of dipeptide amides and dipeptide hydrazides, the amide and hydrazide groups participate in the complex formation.

The structures of 3-33 were assigned on the basis of elemental analyses chromatographic studies, spot tests, ir and nmr spectra. The ir spectra of all the peptides displayed characteristic bands at 3 360, 3 280, 3 080 (NH, CONH, SO₂NH); 2 950, 2 860 (SCH₃); 1 650, 1560 (amide I, II and III); 1 760, 1 720 (C=O); 1 720, 1 440, 1 270 and 1 090 cm⁻¹ (SO₂NH) in support of their structures. The nmr spectra of all *N*-tosyl-di-, -tri- and -tetrapeptides exhibit four aromatic protons in the range δ 7.6-8.41, three methyl (SCH₃) protons at 3.49; the NH amide proton at δ 5.64 and other protons assignable to aromatic and amino acid and peptide residues.

The peptides 3-20, 23-29, 32 and 33 have been prepared for the first time. Methods used for studying copper(II) complexes were the same as described earlier^{8-11, 13, 14}.

Biological screening: The antimicrobial activity of the peptides (3-33) was determined using the hole plate and filter paper disc methods¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Tos-L-Val-L-Met-OMe (7), Tos-L-Met-L-Met-N₂H₅ (20) and Tos-L-Met-Gly-Gly-OMe (24) were found to possess high antimicrobial activities against *Bacillus subtilis* (ICC-strain), *B. cereus* (NRRL-B-569) and *B. mycoides* (USSR) at minimal inhibitory concentration values ranging from 25 to 50 μ g ml⁻¹, and inactive against *Escherichia coli* (NRRL-B-210), *Salmonella typhosa* (NRRL-B-573) and *Penicillium chrysogenum* (MIC 250-500 μ g ml⁻¹). However, the remaining peptides were inactive at test concentrations (250-500 μ g ml⁻¹). Other pharmacological studies are in progress.

Experimental

Samples for analyses were dried at 70°/10 mm over anhydrous P₂O₅ for 36 h. Melting points were determined on an electrothermal melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. All thin layer chromatograms (R_f value) were made on silica gel-G (B.D.H.) using n-butanol-pyridine-acetic acid-water (15:10:3:12) as solvent system and iodine-potassium iodide (20%) as detection reagent. Benzi-

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF *N*-TOSYL-DI-, -TRI- AND -TETRA-PEPTIDES CONTAINING METHIONINE (3-33)[†]

Compd. no.	Peptide*	Yield** %	M.p. °C	R _f	Mol. formula	Elemental Analysis N % : Found/(Calcd.)		[α] _D ²⁵ ***
3	Tos-L-Met-Gly-OMe	60 ^a	117–119	0.79	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	7.48	7.59	+35 (c, 0.1 A)
4	Tos-L-Met-L-Val-OMe	73 ^a	130–132	0.54	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	6.74	6.90	+40.5 (c, 0.3 A)
5	Tos-L-Met-L-Leu-OMe	67 ^b	106–108	0.68	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	6.51	6.60	+22.7 (c, 0.1 A)
6	Tos-Gly-L-Met-OMe	59 ^c	146–148	0.76	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	7.48	7.50	+47.5 (c, 0.1 A)
7	Tos-L-Val-L-Met-OMe	69 ^c	119–121	0.75	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	6.74	6.82	+30.6 (c, 0.2 A)
8	Tos-L-Leu-L-Met-OMe	55 ^c	83–85	0.72	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	6.51	6.55	+17.5 (c, 0.8 A)
9	Tos-L-Met-L-Met-OMe	58 ^c	128–130	0.73	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	6.25	6.30	+80.5 (c, 0.2 B)
10	Tos-L-Met-L-Met-NH ₂	48 ^a	137–139	0.59	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₅ S ₂	9.69	9.79	+7.3 (c, 0.2 B)
11	Tos-Gly-L-Met-NH ₂	70 ^a	209–211	0.68	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₅ S ₂	11.69	11.78	+9.8 (c, 0.2 B)
12	Tos-L-Val-L-Met-NH ₂	67 ^a	186–188	0.60	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₅ S ₂	10.47	10.50	+19.3 (c, 0.3 A)
13	Tos-L-Leu-L-Met-NH ₂	65 ^a	219–221	0.64	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₅ S ₂	10.12	10.23	+9.5 (c, 0.5 B)
14	Tos-L-Met-Gly-N ₂ H ₅	75 ^a	144–146	0.53	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₅ S ₂	14.97	15.04	+22.6 (c, 0.4 C)
15	Tos-L-Met-L-Val-N ₂ H ₅	79 ^a	163–165	0.62	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₅ S ₂	13.46	13.50	+28 (c, 0.6 C)
16	Tos-L-Met-L-Leu-N ₂ H ₅	84 ^a	193–195	0.54	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₅ S ₂	13.02	13.12	+25.5 (c, 0.3 C)
17	Tos-Gly-L-Met-N ₂ H ₅	69 ^a	170–172	0.59	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₅ S ₂	14.97	15.10	+18 (c, 0.7 A)
18	Tos-L-Val-L-Met-N ₂ H ₅	81 ^a	174–176	0.62	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₅ S ₂	13.46	13.47	+41.5 (c, 0.9 C)
19	Tos-L-Leu-L-Met-N ₂ H ₅	79 ^a	149–151	0.56	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₅ S ₂	13.02	13.08	+15 (c, 0.5 C)
20	Tos-L-Met-L-Met-N ₂ H ₅	79 ^a	202–204	0.49	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₅ S ₂	12.50	12.58	+6.5 (c, 0.2 A)
23	Tos-Gly-Gly-L-Met-OMe	63 ^a	200–202	0.93	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	9.74	9.89	+8.6 (c, 0.3 A)
24	Tos-L-Met-Gly-Gly-OMe	67 ^a	222–224	0.89	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	9.74	9.76	+10.5 (c, 0.3 A)
25	Tos-Gly-L-Met-Gly-OMe	75 ^a	129–131	0.90	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	9.74	9.85	+4.7 (c, 0.5 A)
26	Tos-L-Met-Gly-L-Met-OMe	74 ^a	182–184	0.85	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	8.31	8.35	+20.5 (c, 0.6 B)
27	Tos-L-Met-L-Met-Gly-OMe	63 ^a	123–125	0.86	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	8.31	8.39	+24.5 (c, 0.6 B)
28	Tos-Gly-L-Met-L-Met-OMe	68 ^a	167–169	0.88	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₆ S ₂	8.31	8.42	+30.8 (c, 0.3 B)
29	Tos-L-Met-L-Met-L-Met-OMe	63 ^a	134–135	0.83	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₆ S ₄	7.52	7.30	+52.5 (c, 0.2 B)
32	Tos-Gly-Gly-Gly-L-Met-OMe	72 ^a	191–193	0.87	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₇ S ₂	11.47	11.58	+23.6 (c, 0.6 B)
33	Tos-L-Met-Gly-Gly-Gly-OMe	70 ^a	118–120	0.86	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₇ S ₂	11.47	11.60	+72 (c, 0.2 A)

*Abbreviations are those proposed by IUPAC-IUB Commission on Biochemical Nomenclature, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1970, **242**, 6489; 1975, **250**, 3215.

**Crystallisation solvent: ^a ethanol-water, ^b benzene-petroleum ether, ^c methanol-water, ^d absolute ethanol.

***Measured in the solvent: (A) = acetone, (B) = ethanol, (C) = DMF.

†Gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

dine, ninhydrin, silver nitrate and hydroxamate reactions were used for detection of amino acid and peptide derivatives on Whatman No. 1 paper chromatograms (spot reactions)¹⁷. Optical rotations were measured in acetone (A), ethanol (B) and DMF (C), on a Bellingham Stanley polarimeter using 1 dm tube at 25°. The IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Unicam SP 1200 spectrophotometer, and the NMR spectra on a Varian T-60 A spectrophotometer and shifts reported (δ p.p.m.) relative to internal TMS.

HCl-L-Met-OMe (1) and *Tos-L-Met* (2): The compounds were prepared by the procedures described earlier^{6,18}.

N-Tosyldipeptide methyl esters (3-9): *General procedure*: To a cold solution (0°) of *HCl-L-Met-OMe* (1) or any other amino acid methyl ester hydrochloride (0.013 mol) in THF (250 ml) was added Et₃N (1.5 ml) and the solution stirred for 30 min at 0°. The reaction mixture was cooled to -5° and *Tos-L-Met* (2) or any other tosylamino acid (0.011 mol) and DCC (2.06 g) were added to it successively and the mixture stirred for 3 h at 0°, left for 24 h in a refrigerator at 5°, and then for 24 h at room temperature. The precipitated dicyclohexylurea was filtered off and the filtrate treated with glacial acetic acid (0.5 ml) and set aside for 30 min at 20° to precipitate the dissolved dicyclo-

hexylurea. It was filtered, the solvent removed *in vacuo* from the filtrate and the residue recrystallised from ethanol, methanol or their mixtures with water. The dipeptides (3-9) were soluble in DMF, dioxan, THF and alcohols, and insoluble in water and ether. All the dipeptide methyl ester (3-9) were homogeneous on TLC, responded positively to benzidine, and hydroxamate reactions and gave negative ninhydrin test.

N-Tosyldipeptide amides (10-13): *General procedure*: *N-Tosyldipeptide methyl ester* (6-9; 0.001 mol) was dissolved in methanol (150 ml) and the solution saturated with ammonia (0°). The saturated ammonia mixture was placed in a pressure-bottle and kept at room temperature for 48 h. The solvent was removed to dryness under reduced pressure and the residue recrystallised from ethanol, methanol or their mixtures with water. The resultant *N-tosyl dipeptide amides* (10-13) were soluble in DMF, nitromethane, THF and alcohols, and were chromatographically homogeneous (detection with iodine solution and benzidine).

N-Tosyldipeptide hydrazides (14-20): *General procedure*: *N-Tosyldipeptide methyl ester* (3-9; 0.013 mol) was dissolved in ethanol (200 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (85%, 0.035 mol) added to it. The reaction was left for 24 h at room temperature and for 12 h at 5°. The

precipitated hydrazide was filtered and washed several times with cold methanol and finally recrystallised from ethanol-water (1 : 1) mixture. The dipeptide hydrazides (14-20) were chromatographically homogeneous (detection with benzidine, iodine solution and silver nitrate) and gave negative hydroxamate reactions.

HCl.Gly-Gly-OMe (21) and Tos-Gly-Gly (22): The compounds were prepared by the procedures described earlier^{19,20}.

Tos-Gly-Gly-L-Met-OMe (23): It was prepared from Tos-Gly-Gly (22; 0.01 mol), HCl.L-Met-OMe (1, 0.011 mol) and DCC (0.01 mol) using the method described for the preparation of 3-9. The product was purified by repeated recrystallisation from ethanol-water to give chromatographically homogeneous 32 (detection with benzidine and hydroxamate reaction).

Tos-L-Met-Gly-Gly-OMe (24): Tos-L-Met (2; 0.01 mol) and HCl.Gly-Gly-OMe (30; 0.011 mol) were dissolved in THF (150 ml) containing Et₃N (3 ml). The mixture was cooled to -5°, DCC (3.5 g) added to it and the reaction mixture worked up as described for 32. The tripeptide 24 was chromatographically homogeneous (detection with benzidine and iodine solution).

N-Tosyltripeptide methyl esters (25-29): *General procedure*: *N*-Tosyl dipeptide hydrazide (14-20; 0.006 mol) was dissolved in a mixture of acetic acid (8 ml), 5 *N* HCl (4 ml) and water (45 ml) and cooled to -5°. Sodium nitrite (0.53 g) in water (5 ml) was added to it and the mixture stirred for 5 min at -5°. The dipeptide azide was extracted with ethyl acetate (75 ml) and the extract washed successively with H₂O, 5% NaHCO₃ and water, and dried (Na₂SO₄). Compounds 25-29 were prepared by the addition of ethyl acetate solution of the azide to a cooled (-3°) solution of the free amino acid methyl ester (prepared from 0.01 mol of the amino acid methyl ester hydrochloride and 0.9 ml Et₃N as described earlier¹¹) in ethyl acetate (25 ml), and keeping the reaction mixture for 24 h at 0° and for another 24 h at room temperature. It was washed successively with 0.5 *N* HCl, water, 5% NaHCO₃, water, and dried (Na₂SO₄). The solvent was removed and the residue recrystallised from ethanol, methanol or their mixtures with water. All tripeptide methyl esters (25-29) were found to be chromatographically homogeneous (detection with benzidine, iodine solution and hydroxamate reaction) and gave negative ninhydrin reaction.

HCl.Gly-Gly-Gly-OMe (30) and Tos-Gly-Gly-Gly (31): The compounds were prepared by the procedures described earlier^{20,21}.

Tos-Gly-Gly-Gly-L-Met-OMe (32): Tos-Gly-Gly-Gly (31; 0.005 mol) and HCl.L-Met-OMe (1; 0.0055 mol) were dissolved in THF (100 ml) containing

Et₃N (1.5 ml). The reaction mixture was cooled to 0°, DCC (1.3 g, 0.005 mol) added to it and the mixture worked up as described for 23. The tetrapeptide (32) was purified by repeated recrystallisation from ethanol-water to give tlc-pure product. The tetrapeptide (32) was hydrolysed (6 *N* HCl, 100°, 24 h) followed by subsequent chromatography and the hydrolysate yielded two positive spots with ninhydrin corresponding to glycine and methionine.

Tos-L-Met-Gly-Gly-Gly-OMe (33): It was prepared from Tos-L-Met (2; 0.01 mol) and HCl.Gly-Gly-Gly-OMe (30; 0.011 mol) in THF (50 ml)-dioxan (30 ml) mixture using the method described for the preparation of 24. The product was purified by recrystallisation several times from methanol and finally from ethanol-water. The tetrapeptide was chromatographically homogeneous (detection with benzidine, iodine solution and hydroxamate reactions). Complete acid hydrolysis of 33 gave similar results as reported for 32.

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